

A NEW DAMAGE CRITERION FOR COMPOSITES

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A new general damage theory for anisotropic viscoelastic composite material systems has been constructed. The theory is expressed in terms of the stress tensor function and the microstructural intrinsic damage resistance. Deformational damages such as localized sharp flow and molecular orientation, cavitation, and time-dependent volume variation including temperature effects are considered. The bifurcations and instabilities associated with the average molecular distances resulted from unbonded atomic forces and intermolecular attractions create the dominating free volume variations among others. Using series expansion the damage resistance is given in terms of internal and external energies. As a result a new general anisotropic damage criterion is obtained.

A composite material may consist of many phases of reinforcement such as whiskers, particles, or fibers which are bonded together by interphase matrices. The strength and failure behavior is critically important in analysis and design. Damages such as yielding, crazing, and fracturing of the composites are natural consequences of deformation under stress and are considered the result of the variation of the energy density in the media. From the microstructural viewpoint stressing may be visualized as a source of instable process which causes the homogeneous deformation to develop into localized bifurcation. This in turn creates distortional and dilatational changes. In general at any locale when the magnitude of the total energy density \mathcal{E}

reaches a critical value ϵ_c damage will develop. That is when the following condition is met, damage will occur.

$$\epsilon > \epsilon_c . \quad (1)$$

Here ϵ_c is seen as the intrinsic damage resistance to yielding, crazing, and/or fracturing.

The intrinsic damage resistance is dependent upon the intermolecular forces and in turn the interatomic spacings. The average intermolecular distance may be closely associated with the specific free volume Δv characterizing the distance. Hence the damage resistance can be approximated by a function of the specific free volume Δv which is a dimensionless quantity identifying the variation of the volume of the media:

$$\epsilon_c = \Phi(\Delta v) . \quad (2)$$

A general expression for Φ may be obtained by series expansion with respect to Δv [1]

$$\Phi(\Delta v) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a_n (\Delta v)^n \quad (3)$$

where a_n are material parameters dependent upon the microstructural conformation of the medium.

Since most composite systems may be regarded as viscoelastic, the volume variation is expressible by summing the principal strains $\epsilon_I(x,t)$, $\epsilon_{II}(x,t)$ and $\epsilon_{III}(x,t)$ or $\epsilon_{ii}(x,t)$ the normal components of the strain tensor where x represents the spatial coordinates and t is time:

$$\Delta v(x,t) = \varepsilon_I(x,t) + \varepsilon_{II}(x,t) + \varepsilon_{III}(x,t) = \varepsilon_{ij} = \varepsilon_{11}(x,t) + \varepsilon_{22}(x,t) + \varepsilon_{33}(x,t) . \quad (4)$$

From anisotropic linear viscoelasticity, $\varepsilon_{ij}(x,t)$ can be written as the sum of thermal expansion volume and dilatational change as follows:

$$\Delta v(x,t) = \int_{-\infty}^t J_{ijkl}(\xi-\eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \sigma_{kl}(x,\tau) d\tau + \alpha_{ij}\theta(T) \quad (5)$$

with $\xi=t\phi(T)$ and $\eta=\tau\phi(T)$ as defined by the temperature-time shift principle for thermorheologically simple viscoelastic materials. Using (5), the time-, temperature-dependent damage theory can be rewritten as

$$\mathcal{E}(x,T,t) \geq \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a_n \left[\alpha_{ij}\theta(T) + \int_{-\infty}^t J_{ijkl}(\xi-\eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \sigma_{kl}(x,\tau) d\tau \right]^n . \quad (6)$$

where the symbols are reviewed as follows:

- \mathcal{E} is the specific energy per unit volume,
- x are the spatial coordinates,
- T is the absolute temperature,
- t is real time,
- α_{ij} is the summation of the thermal coefficients of expansion,
- $\theta(T)$ is the thermal function,
- $J_{ijkl}(\xi-\eta)$ is the time-dependent anisotropic compliance function with $\xi=t\phi(T)$ and $\eta=\tau\phi(T)$ as the temperature-time shift functions for thermorheologically simple viscoelastic materials,
- $\phi(T)$ is the temperature function,
- σ_{kl} is the stress tensor,
- τ is a dummy time variable, and
- $\dot{\sigma}_{kl}$ is the time derivative of the stress tensor σ_{kl} with respect to τ .

Since a material system can be loaded under a complex state of stressing, multiaxial conditions must be taken into consideration. The available input associated with the deformation up to damage may be divided into two parts. One part is the internal strength that the system possesses and the other part is the energy introduced into the system by stressing. The total energy may be considered as proportional to the product of a tensor β_{ij} and the stress tensor σ_{ij} as given below:

$$\mathcal{E} \sim \beta_{ij}\sigma_{ij} \quad (7)$$

where β_{ij} are the tensor coefficients which are related to functions of the internal and external energies. That is

$$\beta_{ij} = b_{ij} + b_{ijkl}\sigma_{kl} \quad (8)$$

where b_{ij} represent the internal tensor coefficients of the second rank and b_{ijkl} are the anisotropic tensor coefficients of the fourth rank.

The total energy then introduced in the material system at any time t , temperature T , and position x becomes:

$$\mathcal{E}(x, T, t) = b_{ij}\sigma_{ij}(x, T, t) + b_{ijkl}\sigma_{kl}\sigma_{ij}(x, T, t) . \quad (9)$$

The first term on the right hand side of (9) represents the potential energy of the system. The energy introduced by complex loading conditions is represented by the second term.

Combining (9) and (6), a new damage criterion for composites can be written as follows:

$$b_{ij}\sigma_{ij} + b_{ijkl}\sigma_{kl}\sigma_{ij} \geq \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a_n \left[\alpha_{ii}\theta(T) + \int_{-\infty}^t J_{ijkl}(\xi-\eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \sigma_{kl}(x,T,t) dt \right]^n \quad (10)$$

At this stage when $a_0 \neq 0$, and $a_n = 0$ ($n \neq 0$), the above equation reduces to Tsai-Wu's tensor theory [2] and in turn to Tsai-Hill's theory [3,4] for anisotropic composite systems.

The development of their strength theories was originated from the distortional energy theory for yielding of solids. However, it is generally accepted that distortion cannot be separated from dilation in anisotropic composite systems. But based upon the structure of their theories there is no provision for considering the dilatational change of the material system. On the other hand the present theory does provide the possibilities of dealing with both distortion and dilatation. Detailed information will be published elsewhere in the future.

The validity of the present theory can also be seen by considering the strength theories of isotropic material systems [5]. By simplification and reduction of (10) it is also found that the general theory is applicable to not only static but also dynamic loads.

References

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